

Comparison between Two Methods for Adjusting the Rotor Resistance

C. Ben Regaya, F. Farhani, A. Zaafouri, A. Chaari

Abstract – In this paper, the indirect vector control with rotor resistance adaptation is presented, since the command performance depends greatly on the variation of rotor time constant, therefore two adaptive mechanisms have been proposed to identify this constant in order to have a robust control that reflects this kind of change while ensuring decoupling between flux and torque. The first adjustment mechanism based on fuzzy logic, a study was made to present the steps needed to design a fuzzy controller of the rotor resistance. The second mechanism has been developed from an adaptive observer to design an observer for the rotor resistance. Finally, tests show the robust performance of the control law obtained by these two types of adaptive mechanisms. **Copyright © 2012 Praise Worthy Prize S.r.l. - All rights reserved.**

Keywords: Adaptive Observer, Fuzzy Logic, Induction Machine, Indirect Vector Control, Rotor Time Constant

Nomenclature

V_{ds}, V_{qs} : d, q-axis stator voltage components
 i_{ds}, i_{qs} : d, q-axis stator current components
 $V_{\alpha s}, V_{\beta s}$: α , β -axis stator voltage components
 $i_{\alpha s}, i_{\beta s}$: α , β -axis stator current components
 ϕ_{dr}, ϕ_{qr} : d, q-axis rotor flux components
 ϕ_{ds}, ϕ_{qs} : d, q-axis stator flux components
 $\phi_{\alpha s}, \phi_{\beta s}$: α , β -axis rotor flux components
 R_s, R_r : Stator and rotor resistances
 L_s, L_r : Stator and rotor self-inductances
 τ_s, τ_r : Stator and rotor time constant
 M, σ : Mutual inductance and leakage coefficient
 ω_s, ω : Synchronous and rotor angular speed
 ω_{sl} : Slip angular speed
 T_e, T_l : Electromagnetic and load torque
 J : Moment of inertia
 f : Friction coefficient
 n_p : Pole-pair number
 * : Nominal or reference value
 $\Delta R_r = kr = 1/\alpha$: Variation factor of the rotor resistance
 Δk_r : Variation of k_r
 $\Delta \phi_{dr}, \Delta \phi_{qr}$: Difference between nominal and real value
 β : Ratio between stator currents
 P, N, B, M, S, ZE : Denote Positive, Negative, Big, Medium, Small and Zero respectively

Λ : Estimated value
 G : Matrix gain
 $\varepsilon_y, \varepsilon_{i_{ds}}, \varepsilon_{i_{qs}}$: Difference between real and estimated stator currents
 k : Positive gain
 γ : Arbitrary positive gain

I. Introduction

The major drawback of the vector control of induction motors is the rotor resistance variation that is often difficult to identify and varies with the serviceability of the motor, due to temperature variation [1]-[3]. The study of the influence of the variation in rotor time constant on the order proved to be necessary [4]-[7]. For this, several researches has been interested in the development and elaboration of control tools to improve the performance of electric drive systems [8], [9], [13], [14], [15]. The research done in this field showed that the performance of the control study depend heavily on the precision with which the motor parameters are known in particular the rotor resistance, and that a misidentification of these parameters or estimation of quantities to control necessarily lead to a deterioration in performance tuning, especially when the machine is loaded.

Given this drawback, a solution is obtained through the use of fuzzy logic or adaptive observers, which allow the estimation of rotor resistance and reinject it in the control in order to guarantee the decoupling between the torque and flux. [1],[8]. This solution will guarantee a good estimation of the slip pulse when the rotor resistance variations suffered are sudden or slow. This paper presents a comparative study between two types of

mechanism for adjusting the rotor resistance, the first is based on fuzzy logic, the second is going to use an adaptive observer to estimate the value of the resistance R_r .

II. Strategy for Estimating the Rotor Resistance Using Fuzzy Logic

The equations of the machine can be described in a reference connected to the rotating field as follows: [2],[3],[11]:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{i}_{ds} &= \frac{M\phi_{dr}}{\sigma L_s L_r \tau_r} + \frac{M\omega\phi_{qr}}{\sigma L_s L_r} - \frac{1}{\sigma} \left(\frac{1}{\tau_s} + \frac{1-\sigma}{\tau_r} \right) i_{ds} + \\ &+ \omega_s i_{qs} + \frac{1}{\sigma L_s} V_{ds} \\ \dot{i}_{qs} &= -\frac{M\omega\phi_{dr}}{\sigma L_s L_r} + \frac{M\phi_{qr}}{\sigma L_s L_r \tau_r} - \frac{1}{\sigma} \left(\frac{1}{\tau_s} + \frac{1-\sigma}{\tau_r} \right) i_{qs} + \\ &+ \omega_s i_{qs} + \frac{1}{\sigma L_s} V_{qs} \\ \dot{\phi}_{dr} &= -\frac{1}{\tau_r} \phi_{dr} + \omega_{sl} \phi_{qr} + \frac{M}{\tau_r} i_{ds} \\ \dot{\phi}_{qr} &= -\frac{1}{\tau_r} \phi_{qr} - \omega_{sl} \phi_{dr} + \frac{M}{\tau_r} i_{qs} \\ \dot{\omega} &= \frac{n_p}{j} (T_e - T_l) - \frac{f}{j} \omega \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

with i_s, ϕ_r, τ , and L are stator currents, rotor flux, time constant and inductance. The index s and r represent stator and rotor, d and q are the indices of vector components on the direct axis and quadratic, ω is the rotor speed. M and σ are the cyclic mutual inductance and coefficient of dispersion Blondel.

In steady-state we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_{dr} &= \frac{M}{\tau_r} \left(\tau_r i_{ds} + \frac{\tau_r^2}{M} \omega_{sl} \phi_{qr} \right) \\ \phi_{qr} &= \frac{M}{\tau_r} \left(\tau_r i_{qs} - \frac{\tau_r^2}{M} \omega_{sl} \phi_{dr} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

By replacing ϕ_{dr}, ϕ_{qr} with these expressions, the system of equations (2) becomes:

$$\phi_{dr} = \frac{\frac{M}{\tau_r} \left(\frac{1}{\tau_r} i_{ds} + \omega_{sl} i_{qs} \right)}{\left(\frac{1}{\tau_r} \right)^2 + (\omega_{sl})^2}, \phi_{qr} = \frac{\frac{M}{\tau_r} \left(\frac{1}{\tau_r} i_{qs} - \omega_{sl} i_{ds} \right)}{\left(\frac{1}{\tau_r} \right)^2 + (\omega_{sl})^2} \quad (3)$$

Knowing that $\omega_{sl}^* = \frac{R_r^* i_{qs}^*}{L_r^* i_{ds}^*}$, the expressions of flux

following the two axes (d and q) become:

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_r^* &= \phi_{dr}^* = M i_{ds}^* \\ \phi_{qr}^* &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

The system of equations (4) will serve us as a reference model for the mechanism for adjusting the rotor resistance by fuzzy logic. Assuming that the rotor resistance changes its nominal value R_r to $R_r^* + \Delta R_r$, and k_r is the factor for this variation we obtain:

$$k_r = \frac{R_r}{R_r^*} = \frac{1}{\alpha} \quad (5)$$

with $\alpha = \frac{R_r^*}{R_r}$

If we replace the expression of α in the equation system (3) we will have:

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_{dr} &= M i_{ds} \frac{1 + \alpha \beta^2}{1 + (\alpha \beta)^2} \\ \phi_{qr} &= M i_{ds} \frac{\beta(1 - \alpha)}{1 + (\alpha \beta)^2} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

with $\beta = \frac{i_{qs}}{i_{ds}}$ [11],[12].

In the case of an ideal decoupling we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\phi_{dr}}{\phi_r^*} &= \frac{1 + \alpha \beta^2}{1 + (\alpha \beta)^2} \\ \frac{\phi_{qr}}{\phi_r^*} &= \frac{\beta(1 - \alpha)}{1 + (\alpha \beta)^2} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The changing relationship $\frac{\phi_{dr}}{\phi_r^*}$ and $\frac{\phi_{qr}}{\phi_r^*}$ are given in Figs. 1 and 2 as a function of the variable k_r , knowing that the vertical line represents the ideal orientation of the flux. With:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \phi_{dr} &= \phi_r^* - \phi_{dr} \\ \Delta \phi_{qr} &= \phi_{qr}^* - \phi_{qr} = -\phi_{qr} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Figs. 1 and 2 show that:

- For $k_r > 1$, there is increased flux along the two axes (d, q).
- For $k_r < 1$, there is reduced flux along the two axes (d, q).

Therefore and according to the equation system (8), we have:

- For $k_r > 1$, $\Delta \phi_{dr} < 0$ and $\Delta \phi_{qr} < 0$.

- For $k_r > 1$, $\Delta\phi_{dr} > 0$ and $\Delta\phi_{qr} > 0$.

and since $k_r = \frac{R_r}{R_r^*}$ we will have:

- For $k_r > 1 \rightarrow R_r > R_r^* (\tau_r^* > \tau_r)$, we have $\Delta\phi_{dr} < 0$ and $\Delta\phi_{qr} < 0$.
- For $k_r < 1 \rightarrow R_r < R_r^* (\tau_r^* < \tau_r)$, we have $\Delta\phi_{dr} > 0$ and $\Delta\phi_{qr} > 0$.

Fig. 1. Effect of variation of R_r on the shape of the flux ϕ_{dr}

Fig. 2. Effect of variation of R_r on the shape of the flux ϕ_{qr}

The adaptive strategy of fuzzy R_r mechanism is based on two rules described above.

The block diagram of the fuzzy adaptation mechanism used is given in figure below: [10]-[12].

The flux ϕ_{dr} and ϕ_{qr} can be estimated by measuring the currents and stator voltages in accordance with the following steps:

- Estimated stator flux in a rotating field coordinate system related to:

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_{ds} &= \phi_{\alpha s} \cos(\theta_s) + \phi_{\beta s} \sin(\theta_s) \\ \phi_{qs} &= -\phi_{\alpha s} \sin(\theta_s) + \phi_{\beta s} \cos(\theta_s) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

with:

$$\phi_{\alpha s} = \int (V_{\alpha s} - R_s i_{\alpha s}) dt \quad (10)$$

$$\phi_{\beta s} = \int (V_{\beta s} - R_s i_{\beta s}) dt$$

- Estimated rotor flux:

$$\phi_{dr} = \frac{L_r}{M} (\phi_{ds} - L_s \sigma i_{ds}) \quad (11)$$

$$\phi_{qr} = \frac{L_r}{M} (\phi_{qs} - L_s \sigma i_{qs})$$

In our paper we applied the block diagram below by the decoupled control of rotor flux orientation of the Fig. 4 to the induction machine with the use of an estimator of the rotor resistance R_r by fuzzy logic. The universe of discourse is common to all fuzzy variables ($\Delta\phi_{dr}, \Delta\phi_{qr}, \Delta k_r$) and is divided into seven fuzzy sets (NB, NM, NS, Z, PS, PM, PB) with triangular membership functions. [10],[11].

Fig. 3. Schematic diagram of the fuzzy adaptation mechanism of R_r .

We will present the robustness of our proposed control for adaptive control of three phase induction machine. Initially, we will present the simulation results of the indirect vector control with adaptive rotor resistance R_r . Figs. 5(a), 5(b) and 5(c) show the shape of the rotor speed, rotor flux, electromagnetic torque, the phase current and the value of the real and estimated rotor resistance.

Fig. 5(a) shows the effect of sudden change on the shape of direct and quadratic flux. Just at the moment of variation their orientation is lost which affects negatively on the control. Using an estimate of the rotor resistance by the fuzzy logic guarantee the orientation of flux Figs 5(b) and 5(c). The estimated value of R_r is injected into the control to design an adaptive control that takes into account this type of variation. Fig. 6 shows the effect of the change in speed reference for the shape of the flux and the estimated value of R_r , this is due to the large variation of the current $i_{\alpha s}$, which will lead to a misidentification of the rotor resistance.

In the paper [10] the authors propose to add an algorithm to detect the transient to cushion the estimation algorithm.

Or we can use another type of rotor resistance estimator based on adaptive observers to overcome the problem of misidentification of R_r when changing the speed reference.

Fig. 4. Block diagram of vector control with estimation of R_r by fuzzy logic

Fig. 5(a). Simulated results with sudden change of R_r without adaptation

Fig. 5(b). Simulated results with sudden change of R_r with adaptation

Fig. 5(c). Simulated results with slow change of R_r with adaptation

Fig. 6. Simulated results with slow change of R_r with adaptation

III. Strategy for Estimating the Rotor Resistance Using an Adaptive Observer

The model of induction machine can be described in a reference connected to the stator by the following system of equations [2],[3]:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} i_{ds} \\ i_{qs} \\ \phi_{dr} \\ \phi_{qr} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a_1 I & a_2 I - a_3 \omega J \\ a_4 I & a_5 I - \omega J \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} i_{ds} \\ i_{qs} \\ \phi_{dr} \\ \phi_{qr} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 1/\sigma L_s & 0 \\ 0 & 1/\sigma L_s \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} V_{ds} \\ V_{qs} \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{X} &= A_{(\omega)} \cdot X + B \cdot u \\ Y &= [i_{ds} \quad i_{qs}]^T \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

with:

$$\begin{aligned} I &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}; J = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \\ a_1 &= -\frac{1}{\sigma} \left(\frac{1}{\tau_s} + \frac{1-\sigma}{\tau_r} \right); a_2 = \frac{M}{\sigma L_s L_r \tau_r} \\ a_3 &= \frac{M}{\sigma L_s L_r}; a_4 = \frac{M}{\tau_r}; a_5 = -\frac{1}{\tau_r} \end{aligned}$$

III.1. Observation Flux of Induction Machine

The full-order observer that will allow us to estimate the stator currents and flux is given by the following expression:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\hat{X}} &= A_{(\omega)} \hat{X} + Bu + G \varepsilon_y = (A_{(\omega)} - G \cdot C) \hat{X} + Bu + GY \quad (14) \\ \hat{Y} &= C \hat{X} \end{aligned}$$

with: $\varepsilon_y = Y - \hat{Y}$.

The gain matrix G is chosen such that equation (14) will be stable and these poles are proportional to those of the induction machine [2]:

$$G = \begin{bmatrix} g_1 & g_2 & g_3 & g_4 \\ -g_2 & g_1 & -g_4 & g_3 \end{bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

with:

$$g_1 = (1-k) \left(\frac{1}{\sigma \tau_s} + \frac{1-\sigma}{\sigma \tau_r} + \frac{1}{\tau_r} \right); g_2 = (k-1)\omega; k > 0$$

$$g_3 = \frac{\sigma L_s L_r}{M} \left[(1-k^2) \left(\frac{1}{\sigma \tau_s} + \frac{1-\sigma}{\sigma \tau_r} + \frac{M}{\sigma L_s L_r \tau_r} \right) + (k-1) \left(\frac{1}{\sigma \tau_s} + \frac{1-\sigma}{\sigma \tau_r} + \frac{1}{\tau_r} \right) \right]$$

$$g_4 = -\frac{\sigma L_s L_r}{M} (k-1)\omega$$

III.2. Adaptive Scheme for Identification of Rotor Resistance

The variation of rotor resistance is mainly due to temperature variation which is estimated using the adaptive scheme below (Fig. 7).

This scheme is obtained using the Lyapunov stability theorem [2]:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{1}{\hat{\tau}_r} \right) = \frac{\gamma}{L_r} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{ids} (\hat{\phi}_{dr} - M \cdot \hat{i}_{ds}) + \\ + \varepsilon_{iqs} (\hat{\phi}_{qr} - M \cdot \hat{i}_{qs}) \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

where:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_{ids} &= i_{ds} - \hat{i}_{ds} \\ \varepsilon_{iqs} &= i_{qs} - \hat{i}_{qs} \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

γ : Arbitrary positive gain.

Fig. 7. Block diagram of adaptive flux observer

The block diagram of the vector control with adaptive rotor resistance R_r using adaptive observer is shown in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8. Block diagram of vector control with an adaptive observer of rotor resistance R_r .

Figs. 9 show the dynamic responses of the control of induction motor with rotor resistance adaptation by using an adaptive observer.

These figures represent the dynamic responses of rotor flux along the two axes, the actual and estimated value of rotor resistance, the electromagnetic torque and rotor speed for different types of variation of R_r :

- Sudden change;
- Slow variation.

Figs. 9(a) and 9(b) show the shape of the rotor speed, electromagnetic torque, rotor flux along the two axes (d and q) and the value of the real and estimated rotor resistance. We can see the robustness of this estimator

even with a change in speed reference during the estimation period of the rotor resistance.

speed reference, which is not the case with an adaptive observer.

Fig. 9(a). Simulated results with sudden change of R_r with adaptation.

Fig. 9(b). Simulated results with sudden change of R_r with adaptation

TABLE I
PARAMETERS OF INDUCTION MOTOR

Designation	Notations	Rating values
Stator resistance	R_s	2.3Ω
Rotor resistance	R_r	1.83Ω
Stator self-inductance	L_s	261μH
Rotor self-inductance	L_r	261μH
Mutual inductance	M	245μH
Moment of inertia	j	0.03kgm ²
Friction coefficient	f	0.002Nm
Number of poles	n_p	2
Rated power	P_n	1.5kW
Rated voltage	V_{sn}	220V

By comparing the results obtained by the two types of estimators we concluded that the estimator that uses an adaptive observer is more robust than the fuzzy logic estimator for rotor resistance. They also show the superiority of the adaptive mechanism using an adaptive observer compared to using fuzzy logic, because the latter has a misidentification of R_r when changing the

IV. Conclusion

We have presented in this paper the adaptive control of induction motor using two types of adaptive mechanisms to identify the value of rotor resistance, since this type of change led to disorientation of the rotor flux, which can cause instabilities system to control.

The different results illustrate the good performance in terms of quality of response and its role in absorbing disturbances vis-à-vis the reference inputs in the presence of the variation of rotor time constant, which certify the robustness of the vector control using an adaptive observer.

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